

Sources of Parental Anxiety Over Their Children in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State, Nigeria

M. C. Okonkwo

University Counsellor
Anambra State University Uli

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3836821>

Abstract

The study was a survey research to identify the sources of parental anxiety over their children. The study was undertaken in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State. A sample of 300 parents was chosen from the entire population of 500 parents from the six towns that made up Njikoka Local Government Area in Anambra State. The researcher used a questionnaire for data collection. One research question was answered and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and was tested at the 0.5 level of significance. Data were analyzed using independent t-test to test the hypotheses. The findings of the investigation among others were: ten (10) sources of parental anxiety over their children in Njikoka Local government Area of Anambra State. These include career prospect of children in future, children's negative attitude towards religion, and others (see table 1). Also, there is significant difference between mean scores of male and mean scores of female on sources of parental anxiety over their children. Based on these findings, the implications for counsellors were given and conclusions drawn.

Introduction

The effect of anxiety on the social and psychological well-being of people have become a source of concern to counsellors and psychologists alike: Anxiety affects all levels of human beings, and this is shown among parents in their over concern about the welfare of their children. Anxiety is an emotion that has far-reaching effects on human personality and behaviour. When the pressure and strains of life seemed almost too much for a person, anxiety sets. Anxiety is a psychological disorder characterized by distressing, persistent or maladaptive behaviour that induces anxiety (Myers, 1990). Anxiety is a vague, unpleasant feeling accompanied by a premonition that something undesirable is about to happen. The feeling is closely related to the emotion of fear.

Mmaduakonam, (1997) stated that any situation that is clouded with uncertainty, not knowing what will happen, not knowing what is expected, not knowing the best course of action, has a built-in potential for creating anxiety.

Anxiety is a condition in which a person, for no apparent reason, feels uncontrollably tense with, phobic disorder in which an individual feels irrationally afraid of specific object, event or situation, objective compulsive disorder, in which a person is troubled by repetitive thoughts and actions. Anxiety results from psychological problem, such as panic attack which can lead to heart problems, high blood pressure and hypertension that could culminate in cardiac arrest. According to Davidson and Neal (2001), anxiety is the unpleasant feeling which is capable of causing psychological discomfort. It can also be seen as normal innate emotional alarm response to the anticipation of danger or threat or panic. Anxiety being a psychological problem affecting human emotions, may result to psychological disequilibrium in parents, vis-vis their children's behaviours. Thus, it could result from various sources, but parental anxiety has been identified to have link with their children since parents have strong desires for their children's good academic achievement.

Despite enormous problems in Nigeria today, many parents want the best for their children. They want to see them through primary, secondary and university education with good "grades. Many parents are frustrated because of their children's lack of seriousness and factors such as gangsterism, cultism which lead to their frustration. Thus, it was stated that most Nigerians are struggling to make ends meet in our topsy-turvy environment. Illiterates or semi-illiterates expect that all they have failed to achieve will be compensated for, in their children's education. Many of them, in spite of their love for education, find it difficult to pay their children's school fees, and other internal needs which cause their children to be driven out of school. Invariably this will cause anxiety to many parents.

Furthermore, lack of success in examination, poor moral values which could lead children to join cult groups/friends, this will eventually make the female ones to become loose with men, which in turn leads them to experience unwanted pregnancy, while male on the other hand take to armed robbery. Whenever, this situation arises, parents become distressed and devastated and may equally lose psychological balance.

Parents, both literates and illiterates, pray that their children will excel them, because of what is happening in Nigeria's economy, the parents become anxious, always thinking about what will happen to their children in future. Therefore, the study set out to investigate sources of parental anxiety over their children, and also ways of minimizing such anxieties in' Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State.

Statement of Problem

The effect of anxiety on the social and Psychological well-being of people have become a source of concern to counsellors and Psychologists in Njikoka Local Government Area in Anambra State. Some parents especially, parents in towns like, Enugwu-Ukwu, Enugwu-Agidi, Nawfia, Abagana, Abba and Nimo in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State tend to exhibit this anxiety trait over their children and it is becoming a tradition in these towns in Anambra metropolis. This behaviour, the researcher feels calls for urgent attention of counsellors, Psychologists and other helping professionals if parents in these towns are to maintain desirable behaviours and perform successfully in their family functions.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the sources of parental anxiety over their children. Specifically;

- To bring out the sources of parental anxiety over their children.
- To see if gender will influence the parental anxiety over their children.

Scope of the Study

The study was conducted in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State. It centered on finding the sources of parental anxiety over their children.

Research Question

One research question guided the study: What are the sources of parental anxiety over their children?

Research Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study at the .05 level of significance.

-Gender will not significantly influence the mean scores of parents on the sources of anxiety over their children.

-There is no significant difference between the mean scores of parents on the sources of anxiety over their children.

Methodology

The design employed in this study was a survey research. A survey research is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be a representative group of the entire group. Gay (1996), argued that a survey is an attempt to collect data from members of the population in order to determine the current status of that population with respect to one or more variables. The study were carried out in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State. It was made up of six (6) towns. These were Enugwu-Ukwu, EnugwuAgidi, Nawfia, Abagana, Abba and Nimo. This involved all the 300 parents selected from the population to form the sample of the study.

Table I below shows the distribution of parents.

Town	Number of Parents
Enugu-Ukwu	50
Enugu-Agidi	50
Nawfia	50
Abagana	50
Abba	50
Nimo	50

The researcher constructed a questionnaire titled, Questionnaire for Parental Anxiety (QPA)'The instrument had two sections A and B sections.

Section "A" information on personal data such as gender, questionnaire and experience. Section "B" was made up of 15 items, which elicited information on the area sources of parental anxiety over their children. The respondents were requested to indicate the sources of parental anxiety. 4 points modified Likert scale was used as follows:

- Strongly Agree - 4 points
- Agree - 3 points
- Disagree - 2 points
- Strongly Disagree - 1 point.

The face validity of the instrument was established by lecturers who were experts in psychology and guidance and Counselling. Three lecturers in Educational Psychology, Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, looked at the questionnaire items to identify the ones that were really sources of parental anxiety over their children. The experts made their corrections and recommendations which led to some modifications of some items in the questionnaire. Two guidance counsellors were also requested to review the questions in terms of their relevance to the study, and also to state the appropriateness of the instrument to the study. The experts made their criticisms and corrections and gave useful suggestions on the arrangement of the items.

The t-test was used for testing the reliability. The researcher administered the questionnaire on the sample of 300 parents in another Local Government Area under a pilot test so as to avoid undue sensation by the study. After two weeks interval the test was repeated. The sets of scores were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis, a satisfactory coefficient of internal consistency of $r=0.83$ was obtained. The items on the sources of parental anxiety (QPA) were scored as follows: 4 points were assigned to a respondent who endorsed "Strongly Agree", and 3 points to "Agree", 2 points to "Strongly Disagree" and 1 point to "Disagree".

Those with high values of 2.50 and above were given positive interpretation while items with low value of less than 2.50 were given negative interpretations.

Data Analysis and Results: Research Questions:

What are the sources of parental anxiety over their children? Table One: Data Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Sources of Parental Anxiety

S/N	Items	X	SD	Remark
1	Career prospects of my children in future, give me concern.	3.07	0.91	A
2	My children's negative attitude towards religion, upsets me.	2.61	1.14	A
3	My children's behaviour makes me feel worried.	3.17	0.96	A
4	I am afraid of my female children getting pregnant-	2.88	1.21	A
5	Paying of my children's school fees gives me concern.	2.40	1.23	R

6	Providing enough food for my children makes me worry	2.24	0.81'	R
7.	My children's health problems give me concern	3.1	0.82	A
8.	Providing materials needed for my children always worries me.	2.86	0.92	A
9	The moral level of my children give me serious concern.	3.42	0.76	A
10	I become worried whenever I discover that my children keep bad friends.	3.36	0.84	A
11	I am afraid that my children may join cult group, while in school.	2.48	0.95	A
12	Negative peer influences over my children give me concern.	2.65	10-92	A
13	Success in S.S.C.E examination which leads to qualification for admission makes me anxious.	2.56	1.05	A
14	I am worried about my children's success in JAMB examinations for university admission	1.82	0.94	R
15	My children's success in internal examination makes me anxious.	1.9	0.90	R

A=argued: R= rejected

SIN -Serial number of items as in questionnaire

X -Mean values

SD -Standard deviation of rating of subjects.

From Table. 1 above, it is observed that sources of parental anxiety items of S/Nos, 1,2,3,4,7,8,9,10,12 and 13 have mean values of 2.50 and above. They are therefore, 10 sources of parental anxiety that parents in Njikoka Local Government Area have for which counselling is necessary. The other sources of parental anxiety items of S/Nos. 5,6,11,14 and 15 have mean values of less than 2.50. They are therefore, not part of sources of parental anxiety of parents in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State.

Hypotheses One Table Two:

Below shows the data summary of independent t-test of gender on, sources of parental anxiety.

Source	N	X	SD	Df	t-Cal	t-Cri	P
Male	150	41.47	14.31				

Female	150	39.57	14.11	298	3.65	1.96	0.05
--------	-----	-------	-------	-----	------	------	------

From table two above, it is observed that the probability (P) of difference being due to error is greater- than 0.05. At the 0.05 statistical level of significance (95 percent confidence level) the t- cat value 3.65, which is more than the t-critical value which is 1.96. Following the above, therefore, the result showed that there was a significant difference between male parents and female parents on sources of anxiety over their children. $t(298) = 3.65, P < .05$ therefore, the alternative hypothesis that there was no significant difference in the responses of male and female parents anxiety over their children. Table three: t-test of parents on the resources of anxiety over their children.

Source	N	X	SD	df	t-Cal	t-Cri	P
Male	150	41.76	14.31				
				298	1.12	1.96	0.05
Female	150	39.57	14.11				

Table three shows that at 0.05 level of significant and 298 df, the calculated (1.12) is less than critical 1. (1.96). The null hypothesis of no significant difference is therefore accepted. The mean score of male and female parent do not differ significantly.

Summary of the Findings

The major findings of the study were as follows: There were ten (10) sources of parental anxiety over their children in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State. These are as follows:

- ❖ Career prospect of my children in future, gives me concern.
- ❖ My children's negative attitude towards religion, upsets me.
- ❖ My children's behaviour makes me feel worried. I am afraid of my female children getting pregnant.
- ❖ My children's health problems give me concern.
- ❖ Providing materials needed for my children always worries me.
- ❖ The moral level of my children gives me serious concern. .
- ❖ I become worried whenever I discover that my children keep bad friends.
- ❖ Negative peer influence over my children gives me concern.
- ❖ My success in S.S.C.E. examination which leads to qualification for admission, makes me anxious.

Implications for Counsellors:

Counsellors are providers of services for a wide variety of settings including schools, homes and work settings (Okonkwo, 2006). She went further to emphasize that counsellors cannot afford to remain dormant and complacent while the parents are stressed up. The parents both the young and old should come together with the help of counsellors to discuss issues affecting them, so that those of them who were affected will know the right place to look for solution. Therefore, the

counsellors who are the nation builders, with right skills in building should organize seminars, workshops and conferences for parents, children, pupils, students and other adolescent children. This is because the importance of knowing sources of parental anxiety can never be over-emphasized. And so, the counsellors have much roles to play in examining and identifying sources of parental anxiety over their children, for the purpose of national development in Njikoka Local Government Area of Anambra State.

Counsellors should always organize individually and group counselling sessions on regular basis, discussing the sources of parental anxiety over their children and its attendant effects on both the parents, the children and the society at large.

Counsellors should always endeavour to work in collaboration with the government and other stakeholders to instigate the norms, values of community into the children to know the importance and gain of helping their parents and making them happy, so that they may not go on generating anxiety for their parents. May be, this is why Okonkwo (2007) opined that counsellors should teach the young children how to examine their values so that they can appreciate what has real meaning for them. Thus, counsellors should help to teach the adolescents all they ought to know in order to make the society a better place.

Counsellors should come together and provide all the necessary information on sources of anxiety on parents. This could be possible because counsellors are properly placed to use their natural affiliation with adolescents to divulge pertinent information on sources of parental anxiety over their children. The danger of not knowing the sources of parental anxiety should be highlighted, because many of parents suffer anxiety disorder.

Counsellors, together with government and policy makers should provide suggestions/advise that will help to improve the socioeconomic conditions of the nation. This will help to reduce the suffering of the parents which breeds anxiety for them.

Counsellors should make it as a point of duty to alert the government and the policy makers to see the high need of educating children in schools. This is because there is tendency of children behaving well after acquisition of knowledge. Youths therefore should go for higher education which will open their eyes to see and learn themselves and sources of parental anxiety over their children. They will be reminded of the importance of parents, for they are the main sources of livelihood and so should not be hurt.

Conclusion

There is a high need to gear up the services of guidance and counselling for children and society in order to enhance in them more positive attitude towards parents. Inherent in the above is the need for guidance and counselling services for all segments of society and should include students, school staff, parents and guardians, friends and peers and general public so as to educate them with all information about sources of parental anxiety over their children.

REFERENCES

- Davidson, G.O. & Neal, J.M. (2001). *Abnormal Psychology* (8th Ed.). New York: John Wiley.
- Gay, L.R. (1996). *Educational Research Competencies for analyses and Application*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- Myer, E.R. (1990). *The Psychology of adjustment*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.
- Mmaduakonam, A.E. (1997). *Occupational Stress – Counselling the Workers for Survival*. Enugu: Academic Publisher Company.
- Okonkwo, M.C. (2006). "The Competencies Desirable for Effective Teaching of English Language Skills in Secondary Schools: Implications for Counselling" in *Knowledge Builders - a Multi disciplinary Journal for Advancement of Scholarship* Vol. 1 (1).Pp 78-83.
- Okonkwo, M.C. (2007). "The Constraints on Guidance and Counselling Practices in Secondary Schools: Implications for Counsellors" in *Knowledge Builders. A Multi disciplinary Journal for Advancement of Scholarship, Vol.2 (1)Pp. 11-15.*